
GEOTECHNICAL STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS IN NASSARAWA – EGGON
TOWN AND ENVIRONS, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study area lies at the fringe of the Upper Benue Trough and the Basement Complex of Northern Nigeria and specifically between longitude 8°30'E and 8°33'50.3"E and latitude 8°41'9.7"N and 8°45'N. In order to ensure effective geotechnical study of the underlying rocks, ten (10) undisturbed representative samples were taken within a grid of 2.5km by 2.5km. The study established some geotechnical properties of the rocks such as water absorption under saturation with values ranging from 0.52-0.96(%); Compressive strength of rocks of 3.45-89.50(N/mm²); specific gravity of the rocks ranging from 2.5-3.75; with aggregate impact value of rocks ranging from 11.32-21.56 (%) which makes the rock adequate for array of construction material such as roads, foundations, concretes, dimension stones etc. The study characterises the rocks into granite (60 %); Schist (20%); Gneiss (10%) and Basalt (10%) This study is significant as it allows for characterisation of the rocks into rock types for various engineering purposes. This is particularly important for the metropolitan expansion of the relatively new Nasarawa State capital Laia, of which Nasarawa-Eggon falls within its important and immediate emerging urban setting.

KEYWORDS: Water Absorption, Compressive Strength, Specific Gravity, Unconfined Compressive Strength, Aggregate Impact Value

INTRODUCTION

The study area lies within Wamba Sheet 210SW in Nasarawa State of Nigeria and is located in Nassarawa-Eggon LGA. The area lies between longitude 8°30'E and 8°33'50.3"E and latitude 8°41'9.7"N and 8°45'N (Fig. 1). The study area covers an area of about 49 square kilometres (km²) and it is bordered politically to the North by Akwanga, to the East by Wamba, to the West by Doma and to the South by Lafia LGAs. The study area is accessible by a major road that links Akwanga to the state capital (Lafia). Apart from the major road, there are minor roads that criss – cross the study area, making access very easy most especially in the dry season (Mallo et al 2012). The study is significant from the point of view of sourcing of construction material for the emerging cities around Lafia the state capital of Nasarawa State of which Nasarawa-Eggon and Akwanga are major satellite towns worth reckoning with.

Fig. 1: Satellite Image of the Study Area

Methodology

The mapping of the study area was carried out using a scale of 1:50000 topographic maps enlarged to a scale of 1:25000. This map was prepared from Wamba Sheet 210SW. The positions of the representative rock samples were ascertained from Global Positioning System (GPS) readings and fits to the corresponding latitudes and longitudes. Systematic method of sampling was adopted where undisturbed rock samples were collected from different locations during the field mapping exercise at a grid intervals of 2 .5km each and labelled AUS. The Rock samples were subjected to laboratory testing to determine the compressive strength, Specific gravity, the Aggregate Impact values and the Water Absorption Properties of the rocks amongst others.

Geology

The study area is part of the Mada Younger Granite Ring Complex of Nigeria. Jacobson, et al (1958), noted the occurrence of a well defined massif between Akwanga and Lafia as one of the Younger Granite Complexes of Nigeria. Apart from Afu Complex, the south Mada Hill (centred approximately at 8° 25'E, 8° 45' N) is the most southern member of the Younger Granite Complexes of Nigeria. It lies in a NE – SW trending zone which contains the Afu Complex to the SW and some others as the Sharwai, Sha – Kuleri, Ropp, Jarawa and Zaranda to the NE. Fig.1.

Some works have been carried out around the study area which forms part of the Basement Complex of North Central Nigeria. These areas include Akwanga Sheet 209NE and NW. In 1911, Falconer was the first to carry out a geological survey, which was centred on the general geology and geography of Northern Nigeria. In his work, he differentiated the granitic rocks into Older Granites and Younger Granites based on field relations. Jacobson et al. (1958) disclosed the occurrence of the Ring Complex in the Younger Granite Province of Northern Nigeria. Macleod et al. (1971) also pointed out that much of the area is underlain by rocks of the Basement Complex which are all members of a single orogenic cycle (Mallo et al 2012).

However, on a relatively larger scale, the Geological Survey of Nigeria mapped the Akwanga sheet 209 on a scale of 1:100,000. Wright, (1970) worked on the Basement Complex of Northern Nigeria. The field mapping revealed that the about 35% of the study area is composed of biotite granite; 20% gneiss; 10%

microgranite; 5% migmatite/schist; 5% hornblend-biotite granite and about 15% of older-granite and rhyolite (Mallo et al 2012) (Fig. 2).

Fig.2: Digitalized Map of Nasarawa Eggon

Water Absorption

The retention of water in a rock with small pores is greater than in one with large pores and so they are more prone to frost attack. Damage can occur to rocks by alternating wetting and drying. What is more, water in the pores of a rock can expand enough when warmed to cause its disruption. For example when

the temperature of water is raised from 0° – 60°, it expands by some 1.5%. Indeed water can cause expansion within granite ranging from 0.004 to 0.009%. The laboratory analysis of the ten representative samples of rocks is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Rock Test Report for different Rocks of the Area

Sample No.	Density (g/cm ³)	Water Absorption (%)	Water Absorption under Saturation (%)	Diameter of Sample (mm)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Specific Gravity
AU1	2.67	0.91	0.96	54	4.37	2.75
	2.67	0.90	0.96	54	6.11	2.72
	2.64	0.90	0.95	54	7.86	2.72
AU2	2.72	0.88	0.92	54	87.32	2.50
	2.72	0.88	0.90	54	85.57	2.55
	2.72	0.87	0.91	54	89.50	2.50
AU3	2.71	0.85	0.88	54	43.66	2.63
	2.69	0.84	0.86	54	45.84	2.61
	2.67	0.81	0.85	54	44.53	2.63
AU4	2.71	0.82	0.87	54	26.19	2.71
	2.73	0.80	0.84	54	27.50	2.68
	2.71	0.83	0.86	54	23.38	2.66
AU5	2.72	0.85	0.89	54	17.46	2.50
	2.74	0.85	0.87	54	21.83	2.50
	2.70	0.84	0.70	54	18.77	2.51
AU6	2.69	0.89	0.74	54	34.93	3.75
	2.66	0.90	0.74	54	36.67	3.70
	2.71	0.91	0.74	54	35.36	3.71
AU7	2.71	0.85	0.71	54	17.46	3.33
	2.68	0.86	0.71	54	16.15	3.30
	2.65	0.83	0.71	54	18.34	3.33
AU8	2.70	0.80	0.52	54	8.73	2.60
	2.68	0.84	0.52	54	7.86	2.59
	2.65	0.82	0.52	54	9.61	2.57
AU9	2.27	0.99	0.77	54	3.93	2.48
	2.19	1.10	0.77	54	3.49	2.44
	2.25	1.15	0.77	54	3.49	2.41
AU10	2.55	1.17	0.71	54	4.15	2.45
	2.30	1.20	0.81	54	3.49	2.49
	2.48	1.00	0.81	54	3.45	2.43

The engineering classification of rocks is based on strength and/or deformation properties of the rock. The table shows the classification system of the International Society of Rock Mechanics (ISRM, 1978). In this classification, the rock may range from extremely weak to extremely strong depending on the unconfined compressive strength or the approximate field identification Table 2.

Table2. Classification System: The International Society of Rock Mechanics (ISRM, 1978)

Grade	Classification	Field Identification	Unconfined Compressive Strength (MPa)	Examples
R ₀	Extremely weak	Indented by thumbnail	<1	Stiff fault gouge
R ₁	Very weak	Crumble under firm blows & geological hammers; can be peeled with a pocket knife	1-5	Highly weathered or altered rock, shale
R ₂	Weak	Can be peeled with a pocket knife with difficulty; shallow indentations made by a firm blow with point of geological hammer	5-25	Chalk, claystone, potash, marl siltstone, shale, rock salt
R ₃	Medium strong	Cannot be scraped or peeled with a pocket knife; specimen can be fractured with a single firm blow of geological hammer	25-50	Concrete, phyllite, schist, siltstone
R ₄	Strong	Specimen requires more than blow of geological hammer to fracture	50-100	Limestone, marble, sandstone, schist
R ₅	Very strong	Specimen requires many blows of geological hammer to fracture	100-250	Amphibolite, sandstone, basalt, gabbro, gneiss, granodiorite, peridotite, rhyolite, tuff
R ₆	Extremely strong	Specimen can only be chipped with the geological hammer	>250	Fresh basalt, chert, diabase, gneiss, granite, quartzite

Source: (Das, 2006)

The density is defined as the mass per unit volume of material. Since a rock contains grains (solid matrix material) and voids, it is necessary to distinguish between different densities which are related to different parts or components of the rock. Density of rocks depends on the mineral composition, the porosity and the filling material in the voids. The table above list the typical values of density for different rocks. Values of density of rocks (especially granite) of the study area, lies within the range of rocks can be said to be competent in engineering construction and design.

Aggregate Impact Test

Toughness is the property of a material to resist impact. Due to traffic loads, the road stones are subjected to the pounding action or impact and there is possibility of stones breaking into smaller pieces. The road stones should therefore be tough enough to resist fracture under impact. A test designed to evaluate the toughness of stones i.e., the resistance of the stones to fracture under repeated impacts may be called an impact test for road stones.

Impact test may either be carried out on cylindrical stone specimens as in Page Impact test or on stone aggregates as in Aggregate Impact test. The Page Impact test is not carried out now-a-days and has also been omitted from the revised British Standards for testing mineral aggregates. The Aggregate Impact test has been standardized by the British Standards Institution and the Indian Standards Institution.

The aggregate impact value indicates a relative measure of the resistance of an aggregate to a sudden shock or an impact, which in some aggregates differs from its resistance to a slow compressive load. The method of test covers the procedure for determining the aggregate impact value of coarse aggregates.

Aggregate impact value is to classify the rocks in respect of their toughness property as indicated thus:

- < 10% exceptionally strong;
- 10-20% Strong;
- 20-30% satisfactorily for road surfacing;
- > 35% Weak for road surfacing

Source: .Indian Standard Institution. IS 383

The Aggregate Impact Values established from the study reveals values which range from a lowest value of 11.32 to highest values for 14.10 % representing values for granites and Gneiss respectively (Table 3).

Table 3: Aggregate Impact Values of Rocks of the Study Area

Sample No.	Rock Type	Aggregate Impact Value (%)
AU1	Granite	11.86
AU2	Granite	12.71
AU3	Granite	12.15
AU4	Micro granite	14.10
AU5	Granite	14.08
AU6	Granite	13.11
AU7	Basalt	12.70
AU8	Gneiss	11.32
AU9	Schist	21.01
AU10	Schist	21.56

When compared with the above (both the Indian Standard Institution and that of Bell), it shows that most of the rock types in the study area met the minimum requirement to be used for construction (Bell, 2007).

Chief advantage of aggregate impact test is that test equipment and the test procedure are quite simple and it determines the resistance to impact of stones simulating field condition. The test can be performed in a short time even at construction site or at stone quarry, as the apparatus is simple and portable. Well shaped cubical stones provide higher resistance to impact when compared with flaky and elongated stones (Fang et al, 2006).

Applications of Aggregate Impact Value: The aggregate impact test is considered to be an important test to assess the suitability of aggregates as regards the toughness for use in pavement construction. It has been found that for majority of aggregates, the aggregate crushing and aggregate impact values are numerically similar within close limits. But in the case of fine grained highly siliceous aggregate which are less resistant to impact than to crushing, the aggregate impact values are higher (on the average, by about 5) than the aggregate crushing values.

Industrial Applications

The industrial applications of the variety of established rock types in the study area indicates that the sourcing of rock aggregates for construction materials for a fast growing town of Nasarawa-Eggon cannot be over-emphasised. The rocks are within accessible distance and already there are high potentials for small-scale quarrying enterprises to spring up in the study area. However, with the exception of one prominent Small- scale Quarrying Company, majority of existing quarrying businesses are predominantly artisanal quarrying of variety of rock aggregates materials and dimension stones which are easily accessible using rudimentary implements' and are mostly composed of over-lying weathered rocks formations (Plate 1).

Plate 1: Quarrying in the study area

The quarrying of rock aggregates in the town of Nasarawa-Eggon and its environs has contributed to the earning capacities of the women who in collaborations with their male counterparts have effectively established a production synergy that guarantees a complete mine production cycle of rock excavation, fragmentation and marketing of the industrial products to the mutual benefits of all and sundry.

CONCLUSION

The study has established some geotechnical parameters which are vital in the study of the competence of the rock types in Nasarawa- Eggon and its environs especially for the purpose of construction materials. The values of compressive strength, specific gravity, Aggregate Impact Values etc as revealed from the study, are suggestive of the enormous potential that exists for the production of various categories of rock aggregates for civil engineering constructions such as bridges, roads, highways, buildings etc.

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